

CONTEXT-BASED ASPECT LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS FOR CROSS DOMAIN USING IMPROVED BERT

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Abstract

This paper presents efficient contextualizing cross-domain aspect-based sentiment analysis by employing an extended BERT model. The aspect-based sentiment analysis task has been categorized into two different sub-tasks namely: 1) Aspect Extraction and 2) Aspect Based Sentiment Classification. For this purpose, firstly, we extract the aspects (features) from the education performance analysis dataset. Secondly, aspect sentiment classification has been obtained on selected aspects. The existing aspect-based sentiment classifiers are not efficient to extract the local context of words from users' reviews and comments. To address this issue, a novel context base cross-domain ABSA model has been proposed for extracting local context of words in particular sentences. To achieve this, a pretrained model and transfer learning techniques have been utilized to improve the accuracy of the model. The proposed pretrained model has been validated on well-known semeval-14 and self-synthetic educational dataset respectively for University Faculty performance analysis and other domain categories. The results showed that proposed (CD-ABSA) model outperforms in terms of accuracy and f1-score, and these are 94% and 86%, 92% and 80% respectively on two separate datasets as compared to State-of-the-Art similar research with extended BERT.

1. INTRODUCTION

The task of Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) which is widely employed in business, is crucial in natural language processing to identify the aspect terms and forecast the sentiment polarities of those terms. Large-scale labelled data, however, are crucial to the effectiveness of supervised models. As a result, the direction of cross-domain ABSA, which tries to transfer information from a rich labelled

source domain to an unlabeled target domain, looks attractive. Examining the subjective sentiment data in articles and reviews allows people to analyze product sales, service tactics, and lyrical trends. For instance, Amazon and Tmall offer automatic, fine-grained review analysis services, and NGP VAN gives presidential candidates information on social media's emotional tendencies. However, the conventional method of forecasting the

sentiment polarity at the phrase level does not meet all requirements. "This phone has a high battery capacity, but the camera is not good," for instance. We only know if the battery and the camera are appropriate for buyers because the review omitted a comprehensive assessment of the phone. Aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) is used in this instance to do fine-grained sentiment analysis on elements of interest. With the use of ABSA, companies can better grasp users' needs for features of their goods or services [1-6]. In addition, the educational system. The matter of education quality is extensively discussed globally online and offline in public and private education sectors, and it relies heavily on the effectiveness of teaching. Therefore, the precise and effective assessment of teaching has emerged as a significant area of academic research. At the conclusion of every semester, feedback is collected from public and private educational institutions. This feedback aids in understanding faculty performance and student learning. In the past few years, the significance of education that is (student-oriented) has gained important publicity and acknowledgment, with increased emphasis on the viewpoints and voices of students [6-9]. Natural Language Processing (NLP) deeply depends on sentiment analysis. This is a fundamental task in this field, however, sentiment analysis which is applied at the utterance level known as coarse-grained sentiment analysis often falls short of meeting peoples' requirements and acquiring valuable information [5,8-10].

Fine-grained sentiment analysis targets aspects of teaching quality and course content and examines the aspects that students have expressed [8]. The aspects referred to performance teachers and learners. The main aim of (ABSA) identifies aspects of a word and evaluate its sentiment polarity. The task contains two sub-tasks: 1) Aspect Sentiment Classification (ASC) and 2) Aspect Term Extraction (ATE). The ABSA offers a deeper and more comprehensive analysis of insights as compared to sentiment analysis at the utterance level. [7-9] For instance,

the teacher was great, but the content was boring and rough. Can be analyzed through ABSA by extracting the aspects terms "teacher", and "content" and assigning them sentiment polarities of positive and negative, respectively. In aspect-based sentiment analysis, cross-domain analysis is quite challenging and hard, there is a need to enhance the level and interaction of ATE and ASC. The traditional ABSA approaches are focused on the accuracy ASC model while ignoring the relationship between ATE and ASC. Also neglecting the investigation of the ATE extraction and semantic interaction between the two tasks [11-13]. The current ABSA methods limit the ability of the interaction between mutual regulation and multiple tasks between them. In our proposed methodology, we provide a comprehensive and effective end-to-end solution for ABSA. The steps are shown in Figure 01. The ABSA method accurately indicates the aspect term in student feedback "Quality of teaching" is crucial in determining the aspect sentiment, and the aspect term may need adjustments based on whether the sentiment is correct or not [8].

The lack of local information features in word vectors and the blurring of term boundaries, when multiple words are involved, can create challenges in aspect-term extraction. One way to approach this task is by using a BIO tag to annotate the text. Another is to consider it as a sequence labeling problem. However, when determining the current word label on global sequence features may not effectively incorporate the context, resulting in label confusion and aspect term splitting [5-6, 12-15]. For example, in provided text, "quality of food" should be recognized as a single aspect term rather than two separate terms "quality of" and "food". This could result in errors such as an "I" appear before a "B" tag.

Defining the local context scope can pose challenges, this research study [16] employed an effective local context concept and it has the main aim to reduce the impact of non-local Context in ABSA. In addition to this, [11,15-17] developed a systematic method for syntactic dependencies to determine semantics. There are

two major factors helping the difficulty of training effective SA models. Firstly, context-independent word embedding is not enough to capture the semantic and complex sentiment dependences. secondly, recent methods of ABSA datasets are not large to support the training high complex models. In the local context, establishing a predetermined criterion of syntactic proximity is challenging because text

length varies widely [18]. Figure 1 illustrates a sample example of the SemEval Task and an education dataset with labeled aspects and polarity for LOC1, LOC2, and LOC3. The figure helps in identifying and understanding the sentiments and aspects associated with these locations, providing a visual representation of the sentiment analysis results for the given data.

Figure 1: An example from the SemEval Task and education dataset with labels.

The proposed solution for the problem of aspect-based sentiment analysis discussed above in the adaptive aspect-based sentiment analysis model (A-ABSA) presented in the paper, A-ABSA utilizes a combination of adaptive local context methods and local information to attain optimal results on the SemEval-14 task dataset, a frequently used standard dataset for this task [10]. The main contributions of this paper presented as follows:

- To propose a novel CD-ABSA method with context aware and aspect embedding with pretrained BERT model.
- To train model on SemEval Task and education dataset. and investigate SS-LDA approach for aspect extraction.

- To evaluate the accuracy of proposed model by employing well-known performance metrics such as, precision, recall, and f1-score.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a comprehensive review of current literature. Section 3 provides a detailed description of the proposed method CD-ABSA. Section 4 presents experimental results and analysis. Finally, Section 5 includes a concise summary of the key findings.

2. Related Work

The aspect-based sentiment analysis approach involves evaluating the polarity of an aspect's sentiment in the sentences. Presently, sentiment analysis has been carried out by researchers through two methods one is to implement

traditional machine learning, and another is to use more advanced deep learning techniques. Similarly, various authors have employed sentiment analysis using diverse methods which includes hybrid approach, machine learning approach, and lexicon approach; however, less research has been reported on hybrid approaches for students' feedback sentiments analysis. In our literature review, we have summarized sentiment analysis approaches into different categories, and they are explained below.

A. Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA)

Aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) approach used by Rezk, Nermeen Gamal, et al. (2022), involves the use of conditional random fields (CRFs) and hand-designed features to identify aspects and their associated sentiment polarities. Lately, numerous neural network models have been used to analyze ABSA. For instance, X. Li, L. Bing et al. (2015) utilized word embedding that automatically extracted features to tackle the task. Zhou, Xiaotang et al. (2022) proposed a unified framework comprising three key components. Additionally, an interactive multi-task learning network was presented by Nazir, Ambreen et al. (2020) that leverages the interactions between the subtasks of ABSA, while a span-based approach to extract aspects and categorize associated sentiments simultaneously. While these supervised models have shown promising results, they require a large amount of annotated data, which can be challenging to collect in real-world scenarios.

B. Aspect Extraction

ABSA implicates a fundamental task known as ATE, aiming to identify and extract explicit aspects mentioned in each text, on which users have expressed their opinions. Moreover, according to availability data, the ATE is further categorized into three unsupervised, supervised, semi-supervised, and lexicon-based approaches. Initially, ATE was performed with a lexicon-based approach. Later, used hidden Markov (HMM) and conditional random field (CRF)

statical methods for analysis for ATE [1,20-21]. With the advancement and emergence of AI methods, researchers have proposed neural network (NN) models for aspect extraction, which are compared to named entity recognition. While supervised ATE methods are effective, they need a huge quantity of labeled data, particularly while training the NN model. Additionally, named entity recognition frequently uses the Bi-LSTM algorithm. It can be effectively capturing the tree-based dependency information in a sentence, making it less effective for Aspect term extraction. To address this

limitation, models like DTBCSNN and DE-CNN were proposed to capture syntactic and domain-specific features. Moreover, the pre-trained model has also shown improved performance in aspect-based sentiment analysis by modeling contextual embedding. The BERT-GLCLD model further combines global-local contextual information and label-dependent modules to predict aspect terms. The CASE model incorporates external knowledge to enrich word vector information. In a neural network, Zhang et al (12) employed local and global contextual information using NN for improving the efficiency of ATE. A unique Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture with equal width is developed in the current research to include local contextual data. The research goal is to evaluate the efficiency of this novel network topology in aspect term extraction [9-15,18-24].

C. Cross domain ABSA

Supervised ABSA models have been well-developed for a single domain. But, when it comes to real-world conditions where there are texts from multiple or even unfamiliar domains, these models are likely collapsed to deliver satisfactory predictions. The task of aspect-based sentiment analysis is a crucial component of fine-grained sentiment analysis, as it seeks to determine the sentiment expressed towards a specific aspect. In the context of cross-domain Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis. Several studies have focused on the domain adaptation

for coarse-grained sentiment classification, as evidenced by research conducted by Liu, Haoyue (2022), Zhu, Linan (2022), Liu, Ning, and Jianhua Zhao (2022), Ding, Hengbing (2022) Coarse grained categorization is confined to predicting a document's overall emotion. Aspect-based sentiment analysis is a more difficult process since it needs to recognize sentiment expressed towards aspects. When trying cross-domain aspect or opinion phrase extraction, the difficulties associated with the ABSA are exacerbated. Traditional methodologies such as feature engineering and bootstrapping have been employed to allow domain adaptations for aspect extraction [24-28]. Scholars have both employed these methods in their research. In recent years, there has been a significant emphasis on utilizing neural network models. The research combined unsurprised, rule base methods with neural networks to extract the aspects from the different domains, another study introduced a neural network that iteratively adapts to different domains to extract aspects and opinions. However, these studies solely focused on either aspect or opinion extraction and did not identify their correlation. In contrast, presented the first to publish work on sentiment analysis based on cross-domain aspects [20,28-29]. Moreover, the latest studies have placed emphasis on models that utilize neural networks. The researcher combines neural networks with rule-based unsurprised techniques to facilitate cross-domain aspect extraction. In research study [19,31] also developed a recursive neural network for aspect and co-extraction domain adaptability. However, these studies focused solely on the extraction of aspects or opinions with task association. A method for aligning features between different domains was proposed, called selective adversarial learning. However, as the domain discriminator is only trained using the target data, the task classifier is unable to use the category information that is contained in the target data. which is incorporated the transfer learning with ABSA to understand and transfer the knowledge between different subtasks of ABSA, moreover,

the proposed method uses transfer learning, and it allows machines to use multiple data sets and learn from data to do new tasks.

3. Proposed Methodology

This paper presents context-based cross-domain aspect-based sentiment analysis (CD-ABSA) and considers it a labeling for analyzing the aspects and ABSA at the same time. The CD-ABSA uses the high-level representation model to obtain abundant knowledge at various stages. however, in this paper, our proposed CD-ABSA approach, initially used advanced word vector generation and domain vectors to utilizes the transformed-based pre-trained model for classify the CD-ABSA tasks. moreover, for aspect extraction, we used Sentence-segment Latent Dirichlet Allocation (SS-LDA) topic molding method for analyzing the insights of academic data. In Figure 2 showed a comprehensive overview of the proposed CD-ABSA model.

Figure 3 illustrates the embedding process of the Bert model. At the token level, each token occupies a unique position in the vocabulary and is encoded using one-hot encoding. For example, if the vocabulary consists of 10 tokens [CLS, the, course, teacher, truly, helped, in, the, class, activities SEP], the token embedding vector for "CLS" is [1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0], and for

"i" it is [0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0], and so on. we are given a group of combinations $\Omega = \{s_i, a_i\}$ where n is the total number of aspect words in the dataset. It is important to note that a sentence can contain multiple aspect terms. For instance, in a sentence with h aspect words, a_1, \dots, a_h can be different, while s_1, \dots, s_h may have the same value. The target output for this task is a series of predictions $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$, where $s, a,$ and p belong to the set {negative, neutral, positive, and conflict}. Here, s represents the sentence, a denotes the aspect term, and p indicates the sentiment polarity corresponding to each aspect term. For segment embedding, tokens within the same sentence are assigned the same embedding vector. In the original Bert model, the Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) mechanism is used for segment embedding.

However, in this work, we use the Sentence Order Prediction (SOP) to transform it, as explained in Section 3. Lastly, the position embedding vector is added to the tokens, which further enriches the contextual information for the Bert model. For more detailed information, please refer to Section 3.

In the cross-domain ABSA setting, the training datasets consists of a set of labeled sentences from a source domain and set of unlabeled sentences from the target domain. The objective is to utilize

both equations 1 and 2 to train a model using the source domain (DS) and target domain (DT) data, The DS and DT to train model, which can predict the label of test data from target domain.

$$D_S = \{X^S, X^S\}^{NS} \tag{1}$$

$$D = \{X^T\}^{NT} \tag{2}$$

j

Figure 3: BERT Input representation with token, position, and segment.

A. Preparation of academic domain.

This section provides user-given visual information that acts as a supervisory signal for ABSA. It contains two of seed information annotated reviews and aspects. To determine the labeling categories for academic datasets. we need to comprehend the main factors (aspect) of instructors that are considered by management when assessing their quality of teaching. The main factors consist of dimensions that cover execution, course design, evaluation, interpersonal relationships, and Those concerned with delivery technologies. The academic data is collected through an online

Google course evaluation form, which is designed after consultation with academic domain experts. who possess significant experience and insights into the various parameters used to evaluate teaching performance. The course evaluation form includes space for open feedback, which is excluded from performance appraisals since there are no automatic text analytics techniques. The evaluation form filled out by 3000 students from the departments of computer science, software engineering and cyber security, ranging from 1st to 6th semesters, Sindh Madressatul Islam university. Moreover, we merged many terms

having a same meaning or synonyms of each other. For instance, course content and material were combined into main category content. Similarly, terms describing teacher behavior such as selfless, polite, and unbiased and tolerant were combined as behavior. besides, we have also

created general category for those terms that have low score and unimportant from the student's perspective.

Figure 2: The architecture of Cross-domain ABSA

Teaching: The instructional technique that employed in classroom and interactions that occur during learning. The instructor creates an interactive learning environment including various teaching strategies.

Course: its important aspect, typically includes, course descriptions, learning outcomes, objectives and learning materials, projects, and syllabus.

Assessment: its systematic process used by teachers to peer aptitude, skill and knowledge and beliefs to refine student learning

Resource: This also key aspects that belongs available resources and technology provided during teaching, such textbooks, ppt, video and audio lectures.

General: The comments covering all aspects, If the review sentence is intended to describe the overall performance of the teacher without focusing on any specific aspect, it can be written as follows: "Overall, the teacher has demonstrated a commendable performance."

Figure 4 illustrates the size of data containing 20 aspects from three distinct domains: education, laptop, and education. The plot indicates that the sample size for the education domain is greater than the sample sizes for the other two domains. This visual representation provides valuable insights into the distribution of data across the different domains and aspects. Additionally, Figure 5 displays a density chart for comment lengths categorized by

each aspect. The chart suggests a correlation between the aspect classification of targets and the length of their respective reviews.

Figure 4: key Aspects of education and SemEval task.

Figure 5: Density plots of 20 Aspects of education and SemEval task.

Figure 6: Size of sentiment polarity classes (0-3).

Figure 7: Density plots of the polarity classes of education and SemEval task. The polarity category. The

Figure 6 displays the frequency distribution of comments based on their lengths, supporting the observation that user reviews primarily consist of lengths ranging from 0 to 250 tokens. Furthermore, Figure 7 showcases a density chart for comment lengths, categorized by each

chart highlights a connection between the polarity classification of targets and the length of their reviews. Additionally, when a review contains more than 700 tokens, the sentiment polarity of its target is commonly labeled as

(Conflict).

B. Text Pre-processing

Text processing is significant part in ABSA, before feeding student review data as input in proposed CD-ABSA model that need to be ensure that the input text data is in a format that can be effectively analyzed. following steps needs to be implemented first:

Text cleaning: This involves removing irrelevant information such as punctuation, html tags, and special characters.

Stop word removal: This involves removing common words that do not carry meaningful information in text such as (“the”, “and” and “a”).

Tokenization: This is the process of splitting the text into individual words, phrases, or sentences.

Lemmatization and Stemming: This normalization technique includes reducing words to their simplest form.

Part of Speech (POS) tagging: When it comes to ABSA, POS tagging is essential for recognizing sentence features. Each word in a phrase must be given the proper part of speech, which might be a noun, verb, adjective, or another type of word.

C. Sentence-segment LDA (SS-LDA)

SS-LDA is a variation of Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), the statistical model in NLP used for ATE, in the context of academic performance, the LDA aspect extraction is used to identify the key aspects or features shared by students' related teaching performance. The SS-LDA method is suitable in conditions where the topics of interest are related to the overall meaning of a segment of text, rather than individual words. In SS-LDA, once the sentences have been segmented and irrelevant words have been removed, and rest of the keywords are considered as general categories. In student feedback, we have a collection of sentences each comprising of single or multiple aspects related to academics. Moreover, combine these sentence segments in a way same aspect is grouped under the same category. For instance, “teaching skill” and “teaching method” belongs to the “teaching pedagogy” group. For alliance

tasks, the LDA is an effective and operative method. Besides this, the traditional LDA has a data scarcity issue, it does not effective for short text, and have lack co-occurrence patterns, The LDA is being modified by the proposed SS-LDA which is more effective and suitable for short text and any kind of pattern. The LDA approach treats the document as if it were a BoW (bag of words) where the order of the components and their relationships are reflected. The topic modeling of each word is fully dependent on the previous or next words of the document. The effective SS-LDA does not regard itself as a BoW. The topic modeling of each word is not self-determining of previous and next words. The topic modeling in SS-LDA does not occur at the word level, but rather at the level of sentence segment. When a sentence segment assigns a topic, where all the words contained in that sentence segment belong to the same topic.

D. Encoding Layer (BERT)

BERT encoding layer plays integral role in the model, this part of proposed model utilizing the BERT encoder to represent textual sentences. This enables the model effectively to capture the contextual information of different domain and nuance present in the input text.

In the context $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$, where n is the length of the sentence, we create an auxiliary sentence A using methods inspired by Sun et al. [4]. These methods are referred to as QA-M, NLI-M, QA-B, and NLI-B. However, for simplicity and due to similar representations of the auxiliary sentences, we focus only on QA-M and NLI-M.

For each target-aspect pair in the context, the auxiliary sentence A is constructed.

In the context of ABSA, the target-aspect pair is considered as the aspect only, and accordingly, the auxiliary sentence needs to be adjusted accordingly.

Finally, we create the input sequence S by combining both the context C and the auxiliary sentence A as follows:

$$S = [\langle CLS \rangle, C \langle SEP \rangle, A \langle SEP \rangle] \quad (3)$$

$$h^0 = s^{tok} + s^{pos} + s^{neg}$$

(4)

$$i \qquad \qquad \qquad i \quad i$$

$$\qquad \qquad \qquad \qquad i$$

In equation (03), where <CLS> is a unique token representing each sequence for classification, and <SEP> is the token used to separate the context C and the auxiliary sentence A.

For each given token s_i in S, its input representation is constructed as followed by equation (04):

E. Contextualized embedding layer (CEL)

In NLP, the word embedding enables the conversion of words into sparse one hot vector or called dense representation. It's a type of representation that allows words with similar meanings or representations. One notable benefit of utilizing word embedding is to partially capture the word sense and syntax. While static word embedding like Glove remains unchanged, certain aspect terms may be domain-specific and their classification as an aspect term can vary depending on the content and specific task. Such as the ATE. For example, "The assignments in this course were challenging but fair, while the grading scheme was confusing and unclear." In this context, "assignments" and "grading scheme" are the aspect terms being evaluated. "Challenging but fair" refers to the level of difficulty of the assignments, while "confusing and unclear" describes the way the grading scheme was presented to students. The word embedding have different meaning in a different context. One possible approach is to utilize contextualized word embedding like BERT. These embeddings may accurately capture a word's meaning and generate many word embeddings for the same word in various circumstances. Therefore, the present study proposes a contextualized embedding layer for this purpose. A more recent language representation approach is BERT, which is an autoencoder language model, as opposed to ELMo [57], which uses LSTM as its main architecture,

and CPT [58], which models phrase flow via unidirectional transformers. BERT successfully captures contextual information by masking off certain words in a phrase during training and then learning to anticipate those masked words. The BERT can effectively capture bidirectional information in a sentence and generate contextualized word embeddings.

The basic BERT is categorized into two types of parameter models, BERTBase and BERTLarge. The BERTBase contains 12 layers and 12 heads in the multi-head attention technique, a hidden size of 768, and approximately 110 million parameters. The BERTLarge is an extended version of BERT, with 24 transformers layers instead of 12, and 16 attention heads. The dimensionality of output representations of the transformers' encoder is also increased to 1024, compared to 768 in BERTBase. The results larger model size with about 340 million parameters in BERTBase. The larger model size allows BERTLarge to capture more complex relationships between words and better handle tasks that require a deeper understanding of language. However, the larger model size also requires more computational resources to train and use.

The input phrases for the Aspect Term Extraction (ATE) challenge are transformed into token sequences before being processed for BERT. A special symbol, [CLS], is appended to the beginning of the sentence $S = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{n-1}, w_n\}$, and another special symbol, [SEP], is added at the last of the phrase S. This yields the token sequence $S_{input} = \{[CLS], w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{n-1}, w_n, [SEP]\}$. The "S" word sequence has a length represented by the symbol n.

Figure 3 depicts the input preparation procedure. Equations (05) defines the contextualized embedding layer's output representation.

$$H_{bert} = BERT(S_{input}) \tag{5}$$

H_{bert} represents the BERT output matrix with dimensions $H_{bert} \in \mathbb{R}^{|S_{input}| \times d}$ in the given context, where $|S_{input}| = n+2$. Here, n represents the entire length of the original phrase S, and d denotes the BERT output dimension. BERT comprises all operations

done by the BERT model, where S_{input} specifies the overall length of the input after transformation.

The BERT model's output representations are transferred to the layer below, denoted as h_{BERT} , $i \in [1, n]$, where i takes values in the range $[1, n]$, with the exception of the rest of the representations of the unique tokens [SEQ] and [CLS], which are specifically represented as $h_{BERT|cls}$ and $h_{BERT|seq}$ respectively.

F. Output Layer (BERT)

In output layer, the result mitigates, a dropout layer is used for the gating layer. The final fully connected layer with softmax function and used vector. The output of the [CLS] token, the sentence-level representation, is then passed through a dense, fully connected layer. This dense layer aids in capturing crucial characteristics for the cross-domain ABSA task and decreases the representation's dimensionality. Across all data samples, the model minimizes the cross-entropy loss between the actual sentiment labels ("y") and the projected values ("x"). This method increases the model's capacity for generalization and strengthens its handling of unknown data.

The ground truth y and predicated value \hat{y} for all data samples. Where i is the index of a data

sample, j is the index of a sentiment class as represented in equation (06).

$$L = - \sum_i \sum_j y^j \log y^j \tag{6}$$

4. Result and Discussion

In this section, quantitative results have been discussed for our proposed aspect-based sentiment analysis model. For this purpose, a performance evaluation of our proposed method has been achieved using three well-known datasets namely, academic reviews (Faculty and Course Evaluation), SemEval 2014 datasets of restaurant and laptop reviews, and the Twitter dataset for social media news stories. The Restaurant dataset contains valuable information regarding diners' opinions on various aspects such as food quality, service, and other factors related to establishments. Similarly, the laptop dataset comprises of consumer reviews of electronic items obtained via an e-commerce platform. The academic dataset was gathered to analyze the emotional data of students and primarily focuses on categorizing sentiments into three labels: positive, neutral, and negative. For a comprehensive overview of the experimental dataset statistics, please refer to

Table. 1 List of hyperparameters for enhanced BERT Algorithm.

Hyperparameters	Value
Batch Size	64
Learning Rate	0.01
Dropout Rate	0.2
Epochs	20
Max sequence length	150
Vocab Size	12000
Optimizer	Adam
Embedding	512
Attention layers	12
Hidden layers	12

BERT is a transformer-based model that underwent self-supervised pretraining utilizing a sizable amount of English data. This shows that it received pretraining just on unannotated raw

texts, enabling it to use data that is available to the public. In the pretraining process, inputs and labels were generated automatically from the supplied texts, enabling it to collect detailed

contextual information and perform well across a range of NLP tasks. In the BERT model, each word is represented as a 768-dimensional vector. The model has 300 capsule layers and 12 transformer layers. We use a sentiment matrix with a dimension of 300 and three sentiment capsules as part of the sentiment analysis methodology. We set the dropout parameter to 0.1 and the regularization parameter to a value of 0.08 to manage regularization. The Adam optimizer is used

[35] to increase the model's performance during training. We use the Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) function for adversarial training. Both are set to 0.3, with the perturbation step size (ϵ) being set to 0.25. For all three of the datasets, we divided the validation set and training set in an 8:2 ratio to ensure proper data division. The best version of the model is kept for further evaluation and hyperparameter adjustment on the validation dataset. The model is periodically stored throughout the training phase. There are 30 epochs and 16 batches in the training procedure. Next, we assessed the performance of our BERT-based model on each dataset using

standard evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. We compared our results with existing state-of-the-art models to demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach. In our experiments, we approached the dataset as a binary classification task, even though it originally had three sentiment labels. Instances that express positive emotions were categorized as positive samples, while instances displaying negative or neutral emotions were considered negative samples. To clarify, let's define the following terms: TP shows the positive samples that were accurately expected to be positive, TN represents the negative samples correctly expected to have a negative or neutral sentiment, and FP represents the samples that are negative and incorrectly forecasted to have a negative or neutral sentiment. Likewise, when considering the neutral sentiment label, the negative sample encompasses both positive and negative emotional data.

Our experiments revealed that our BERT-based model performed well on all three datasets. It efficiently caught the sentiments of many areas within the evaluations, providing us with greater

Figure 8: The accuracy of cross-domain aspect classification.

insights into user thoughts. The model showed

excellent cross-domain generalization, effectively predicting sentiment in a variety of

circumstances. In addition, we examined the model's strengths and weaknesses to conduct a thorough review of its performance. We discovered certain issues, such as dealing with domain-specific language and

capturing complex thoughts, that may be

addressed further in future studies. Overall, the findings of our BERT-based language model in cross-domain aspect-based sentiment analysis were encouraging. The findings demonstrate the value of using pre-trained models like BERT for sentiment analysis tasks and give useful insights for sentiment analysis across domains.

Figure 9: The losses of cross-domain aspect classification.

These visualizations and results provide valuable insights into the model's effectiveness and progress during training. In model, Figures 8 and 9 showcase the performance of the CD-ABSA model on aspect classification of 20 key major classes, including Course, General, Teacher, Resource, Assessment, Knowledge, Food, Service, Price, Place, Prices, Staff, Screen, Menu, Dinner, Use, Atmosphere, Battery Life, Battery, and Pizza. In Figure 8, the loss of the model is depicted over 30 epochs, revealing a gradual decrease in loss as the performance improves. This observation is consistent with the findings

presented in Figure 9 and Table 4. Figures 11 and 12 illustrate the performance of the CD-ABSA model on Polarity classification with 4 classes (Positive, Negative, Neutral, and Conflict). In Figure 12, the loss of the model is shown with respect to the (30) epochs. It is observed that the proposed model loss decreases gradually as the performance improves on certain epochs, as demonstrated in

Figure 11. The graphs provide valuable insights into the model's learning process and how it evolves over the course of training. Figure 10

displays the confusion matrix representing the prediction summary for aspect-based sentiment analysis on 20 key aspect classes. The matrix shows the count of correct and incorrect predictions for each class. The results indicate that the performance on education aspect classes is better, primarily due to the larger sample size available for these classes. Figure 13 illustrates the confusion matrix for sentiment polarity classification, encompassing four distinct classes: Positive, Negative, Neutral,

and Conflict. The results indicate a noticeably higher frequency of neutral polarity classifications when compared to the other classes.

Table. 2 Overall performance models on three datasets, we use accuracy and F1 score measuring the performance of methods various methods (etc), the underlined values are the performing of the baseline models. The bolded part is the best result.

Category	Method	Education		Restaurant		Laptop		Twitter	
		F1	Acc	F1	Acc	F1	Acc	F1	Acc
Att Networks	MGAN	~	~	71.27	80.69	71.75	76.54	74.90	73.60
	BERT-base	~	~	80.22	86.31	76.11	79.66	75.23	76.20
	RAM	~	~	80.22	86.31	71.35	74.49	69.36	67.30
Syn	DualGCN	~	~	71.27	80.69	71.75	76.54	74.90	73.60
	RGAT	~	~	80.22	86.31	76.11	79.66	75.23	76.20
	CDT	~	~	80.22	86.31	71.35	74.49	69.36	67.30
Aug	TNET	~	~	71.27	80.69	71.75	76.54	74.90	73.60
	CBERT	~	~	80.22	86.31	76.11	79.66	75.23	76.20
	BT + BERT	~	~	80.22	86.31	71.35	74.49	69.36	67.30
Att and LDA	SS-LDA+BERT	92.80	94.20	<u>80.22</u>	<u>86.31</u>	<u>71.35</u>	<u>74.49</u>	<u>69.36</u>	<u>67.30</u>

Table. 3 List of hyperparameters for enhanced BERT Algorithm.

Domain	Aspect	P	R	F1	Accuracy
Education Reviews	Positive	0.89	0.90	0.94	0.90
	Negative	0.92	0.86	0.82	0.92
	Neutral	0.90	0.91	0.90	0.91
	Conflict	0.83	0.83	0.82	0.88
Restaurant Reviews	Positive	0.80	0.51	0.55	0.94
	Negative	0.79	0.80	0.79	0.94
	Neutral	0.41	0.46	0.43	0.94
	Conflict	0.85	0.88	0.	0.94
Laptop Reviews	Positive	0.72	0.66	0.49	0.94
	Negative	0.74	0.66	0.46	0.94
	Neutral	0.73	0.66	0.47	0.94
	Conflict	0.60	0.59	0.55	0.74

Table. 4 The size of experimental datasets with sentiment polarity for Cross domain.

Dataset	Samples	Sentence	#Positive	#Negative	#Neutral	#Conflict
Education Reviews	Train	9780	4997	4958	2223	901
	Test	3300	1310	1300	500	190

Restaurant Reviews	Train	1980	2164	805	633	91
	Test	599	727	196	196	39
Laptop Reviews	Train	1454	976	851	455	45
	Test	409	337	128	167	12

For fine-grained datasets, the number of sentiment labels can exceed the number of sentences, as a single sentence may contain multiple sentiments. Conversely, for coarse-grained datasets, each sentence is associated with only one sentiment. To ensure sample uniformity,

datasets with sentiment scores ranging from 1 to 5 have an equal number of samples for each score, and datasets with three sentiment categories also have an equal number of samples for each category. Table 4 showcases some examples from each dataset for reference.

Figure 10: Aspect wise predication classification of model.

Table. 5 Classification Report of 20 top aspects CD-ABSA.

Aspect	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Support
Course	0.87%	0.95%	0.91%	1031
General	0.76%	0.72%	0.74%	237

Teacher	0.72%	0.62%	0.67%	220
Resource	0.80%	0.72%	0.76%	216
Assessment	0.76%	0.63%	0.69%	205
Knowledge	0.94%	0.97%	0.95%	64
Food	0.58%	0.59%	0.59%	49
Service	0.65%	0.67%	0.66%	70
Price	0.86%	0.86%	0.86%	14
Place	0.75%	0.67%	0.71%	9
Prices	0.60%	0.38%	0.46%	8
Staff	0.60%	0.75%	0.67%	8
Screen	1.00%	0.89%	0.94%	9
Menu	0.86%	0.92%	0.89%	13
Dinner	100%	100%	100%	4
Use	0.80%	0.80%	0.80%	5
Atmosphere	0.60%	0.75%	0.67%	6
Battery Life	0.62%	0.63%	0.71	6
Battery	100%	0.71%	0.83%	7
Pizza	100%	100%	100%	10

Figure 11: The accuracy of cross-domain polarity classification.

Figure 12: The losses of cross-domain polarity classification.

Figure 13: Aspect wise predication classification of model.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper introduces a novel approach for cross-domain aspect-based sentiment analysis. In this research study, we trained our model on three distinct domains such as (Laptop, Restaurant and Education) and tested on other. To cater contextual information, the proposed CD-ABSA model used the extended pretrained bert-base-based for aspect and sentiment polarity classification. The CD-ABSA model uses the automated SS-LDA for aspects extractions in education domain. The evaluation of the model includes various metrics such as precision, recall, F1 score, and accuracy. The results demonstrate that the proposed CD-ABSA model achieves exceptional accuracy across all three domains. Additionally, the model is further tested on hotel reviews datasets, showing its versatility and robustness. We prove the performance is obviously improved compared with other models by extensive experiments on Semeval-2014 and education dataset. The current datasets are unbalanced, in future, this work shall be extended.

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